

ISic1658

I.Sicily inscription 1658

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ έτε[λε]ύτησεν [ό]
2. υιοϋς ήμϋν
3. Ποτετάς έτέων
4. [ό]κτώ μηνι Άγόστϋ
5. τ[ή]ς δεκά(της) και Ζό[η]Ε]
6. λ[έ]νη έν[ν]εακε
7. δεκάτη(ς) □

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494032

EDCS 41400015

EDCS 41400016

PHI 175735

PHI 331990

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 41.0823

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 39.1016

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 27.0685

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1152

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 132

Griesheimer, M. 1989. Quelques inscriptions chrétiennes de Sicile orientale. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 65: 143-177. At 165 no.12 fig. 14

Ferrua, A 1974. Review of M.T. Manni Piraino, Iscrizioni Greche lapidarie del museo di Palermo (1973). *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 50: 431-433. At 432-433

Worp, K.A. 1991. Remarks on weekdays in Late Antiquity occurring in documentary sources. *Tyche*. 6: 221-230. At 228-229

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia. Vatican. At no.498

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1658. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354755>